

Possible Antiparkinson Compounds : Part I : Synthesis of Some 2-Aryl-3-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones

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2-Aryl-benzoxazin-4-ones (II, X=H, Br; R=C₆H₅, C₆H₅CH=CH) are condensed with 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (III, R'=H, CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₄H₉, i-C₄H₉, n-C₆H₅, i-C₄H₉) to give 2-aryl-3-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (IV). These compounds have no significant antitremorine activity, and they produce negligible hypothermia.

THE thiadiazole derivatives have been reported to possess enhanced CNS depressant, anticonvulsant¹ and antiparkinson properties². Further, a large number of quinazolinones have been shown to be CNS depressant³⁻⁵, anticonvulsant^{6,7} and muscle relaxants^{8,9}. Tiwari and Pandey¹⁰ have also done some work on quinazolinone derivatives. So it was worthwhile to investigate whether the compounds having both thiadiazole and quinazolinone moieties can have better pharmacological activity. Synthesis of some 2-aryl-3-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)quinazolin-4(3H)-ones and assessment of their antiparkinsonism activity are described in this paper.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route :

Experimental

2-Aryl-benzoxazinones(II) – A mixture of anthranilic acid or 3,5-dibromoanthranilic acid¹¹ (0.01 mole) and the appropriate acid chloride (0.02 mole) was stirred in anhydrous pyridine (35 ml) for 2 hrs. The reaction was exothermic, therefore cooling was

also done occasionally during stirring. The mixture was diluted with water, the separated solid filtered, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, and finally recrystallised from alcohol.

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(III) – These were prepared by the method given by Funatsukuri *et al.*¹². A mixture of the alkyl carboxylic acid (0.1 mole) and thiasemicarbazide (0.1 mole) in excess of sulphuric acid (A.R.) was refluxed for 6 hrs. Subsequently, the mixture was cooled, poured into excess of ice water, and neutralised with ammonia to precipitate the product.

2-Aryl-3-(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (IV) – The benzoxazinone(II) (0.005 mole) and 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole(III) (0.005 mole) were refluxed together in pyridine (20 ml) for about 6 hrs. Subsequently, after cooling to room temperature it was poured in a mixture containing conc. HCl (100 ml) and crushed ice (100 g), when the solid product was separated out. The solid was filtered at the pump and washed repeatedly with cold water. It was dried and crystallised from alcohol or alcohol water.

Various quinazolinones(IV) thus synthesised in 55-60% yield are listed in Table I.

Pharmacology :

Six compounds (marked by asterisks in Table I) were subjected for their toxicity test¹³ (determination of ALD₅₀ values) and antitremorine activity. All the compounds were well tolerated by albino mice even up to the doses of 1000 mg/kg without any toxic manifestations. This observation indicated the non-toxicity of these quinazolinones.

For antitremor activity, the albino mice of either sex were chosen. The compound under screening was given intraperitoneally. One hour after the drug administration, oxo-tremorine

(dissolved in water) was given to mice intraperitoneally. None of the compound was found to possess significant antitremorine activity.

TABLE-1: 2-ARYL-3-(1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)-QUINAZOLIN-4-(3H)-ONES (IV)†

Sl. N.	R	R'	X	m.p. °C‡
a.	-C ₆ H ₅	-H	H	250
b.*	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃	H	217
c.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₃	H	210
d.	-C ₆ H ₅	-n-C ₇ H ₇	H	185
e.*	-C ₆ H ₅	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-$	H	220
f.*	-C ₆ H ₅	-n-C ₄ H ₉	H	183
g.	-C ₆ H ₅	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$	H	200
h.*	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-H	H	243
i.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-CH ₃	H	186
j.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-CH ₂ CH ₃	H	210
k.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-n-C ₇ H ₇	H	189
l.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-$	H	195
m.*	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-n-C ₄ H ₉	H	191
n.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$	H	205
o.	-C ₆ H ₅	-H	Br	211
p.*	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃	Br	196
q.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₃	Br	220
r.	-C ₆ H ₅	-n-C ₇ H ₇	Br	190
s.	-C ₆ H ₅	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-$	Br	240
t.	-C ₆ H ₅	-n-C ₄ H ₉	Br	193
u.	-C ₆ H ₅	$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix} \rangle \text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$	Br	200

† All the compounds gave correct analysis for nitrogen.
‡ The melting points are uncorrected.

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The compounds produced negligible hypothermia (not more than 1.0° at 200 i.p.). The SMA also decreased by slight degree.